

PERCEPTIONS OF STAKEHOLDERS ABOUT SCHOOL HEAD LEADERSHIP STYLE PRACTICE AND TEACHERS' PRODUCTIVITY IN SCHOOLS IN THE NORTH CENTRAL GEOGRAPHICAL ZONE, NIGERIA

¹Omuya Ohunene Florence (PhD) and ²Haruna Josephine Eleojo (PhD) and ³Tolorunleke Emmanuel Adebayo (PhD)

0000-0002-4288-783X¹ 0009-0002-3381-8688², & 0000-0002-9345-5375³

Email: Florence.omuya@fulokoja.edu.ng¹, Josephine.haruna@fulokoja.edu.ng², and tolorunleke.adebayo@fulokoja.edu.ng³

Phone: 08065638085, 08036459331, and 08030726340

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Abstract

The perceptions of stakeholders regarding school head leadership practices style on teachers' productivity in schools play an important aspect in school administration. This study examined the influence of school heads' leadership styles and paternalistic leadership styles on teachers' productivity. A self-structured questionnaire tagged "Perceptions of stakeholders on school heads leadership style practices on teachers' productivity (PSSHLSTP)" was used to elicit respondents (school heads, teachers, Ministry of Education Officials and Executive Officials of Parents Teachers Associations) with a sample size of 345 school heads, 321 Ministry of Education Officials, 382 teachers, and 378 PTA Officials. Analysis of variance was used to test the null hypothesis postulated at a significance level of 0.05. The analysis of the findings showed that school heads that use situational leadership style make use of different leadership styles as the need arises, which results in high productivity of teachers. Furthermore, the school heads that deployed paternalistic leadership style tend to be fair and play fatherly figure or motherly figure to the teachers when delegating duties to them, and this has resulted in high productivity among teachers because of too much familiarity.

1. Introduction

The perceptions of stakeholders regarding school head leadership styles and teacher productivity are relevant to the effectiveness and efficiency of school head administration. The school as a formal organization managed by a headteacher who oversees the overall administration of the school needs to be acquainted with different

^{1,2,3}Department of Educational Foundations, Faculty of Education, Federal University Lokoja, Kogi State - Nigeria

leadership styles that can enhance the teacher's productivity. Jumare (2015) argued that the proper use of leadership style by the school head is one of the most important aspects of achieving organizational goals. However, a lack of understanding on the use of appropriate leadership styles by school heads has become a challenge to efficiency and effectiveness in school administration, which has hampered teachers' productivity. Previous research has largely investigated the role of leadership in school administration and emphasized that the collaboration of leadership processes among school administration leads to teamwork that makes the administrative roles of school heads effective (Haruna, 2022).

Recent studies have examined stakeholders' perceptions of school head leadership styles. This study builds on this evidence by examining the effect of situational leadership styles and the paternalistic leadership styles of school heads on teachers' productivity within the Nigerian Secondary School context. Previous research has shown that the leadership style of school heads has a significant impact on the efficiency and effectiveness of school administration (David, 2012, Adeyemi, 2010, Hassan, 2011 & Obonyo et al, 2017). Leadership styles are often perceived as a factor linked to the efficiency and effectiveness of a school administration that has a positive outcome on students and the learning environment. This study aims to contribute to additional evidence in the area of comparing the perception of stakeholders on situational leadership styles and the paternalistic leadership styles of school heads. This will support the understanding of school heads in varying their leadership styles as a school administrator. This study addressed the following research questions and null hypotheses by examining interactions between school heads, teachers, ministry of education officials, and effective members of parent's teacher associations.

2. Research Questions

The following research questions were used to guide the study:

1. How do the stakeholders perceive school head situational leadership style practices on teachers' productivity?
2. How do stakeholders perceive the effect of school head paternalistic leadership style practices on teachers' productivity?

3. Research Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were proposed for the study.

1. There is no significant difference among the perceptions of school heads, teachers, and Ministry of Education officials regarding school head situational leadership style practices on teacher productivity.
2. There is no significant difference among the perceptions of School Head, Teachers, Ministry of Education officials, and PTA Executive Officers on the effect of school head paternalistic leadership style practices on teachers' productivity.

4. Literature Review

Perception of Leadership Style

The perception of leadership styles of heads can be defined as the way in which people view, understand, or interpret how school heads utilize various leadership styles to discharge their leadership and administrative roles (Haruna et al, 2022). The perception of stakeholders on school heads' leadership styles was found to influence teachers' performance at a moderate level, while teachers' job performance was found to be better in schools where school heads deploy or use autocratic leadership styles (Adeyemi, 2010). A study carried out by Brenda (2011) shows that school heads and teachers are active participants in developing adequate use of leadership styles to run the management of schools. Also, recent literature has shown that the perception of stakeholders regarding

school heads' leadership styles has shaped the understanding of headteachers regarding their roles as administrators (Obiwuru, Okwu, Akpa & Nwankere, 2011).

Peter (2015) examined the relationship between leadership styles used by headteachers in public secondary schools and students' academic achievement in Kericho, Kenya, with 119 school heads and 1060 teachers as participants and found out that headteachers' leadership styles have a strong relation with the K.C.S.E. result. Recent studies have shown that school leadership plays an important role in shaping the destiny of a school, from goal setting to goal accomplishment. Deepack, Suman, and Rajiv (2013) discussed the link between a school's effectiveness and its leadership.

The literature on situational leadership style has also identified a comparable relationship between school head and teacher performance. This was reflected in the work of Omuya (2021), who showed that school heads vary their leadership styles according to the situation in the school setting. Adeyemi (2010) saw the leadership style of school heads as a social influencing process for the attainment of goals; thus, a leader needs to have adequate knowledge of various styles of leadership that are suitable to exercise their power, authority, the mobilizing of resources and influencing the behavior of the teachers to move toward chosen direction and to achieve the objectives and goals of the organization.

Situational Leadership Style

Leadership styles in an organization play a significant role in enhancing or delaying the interest and commitment of individuals in an organization (Omuya et al, 2021). Situational leadership styles are influenced by leaders choosing the best course of action based on situational conditions or circumstances (Bagobiri & Kassah, 2009). Due to the increased attention of school heads to be accountable for their teachers' productivity, choosing a situational leadership style is crucial, as it plays an instrumental role in enhancing teachers' performance (Olu, 2020).

However, several studies have been conducted on the grounds that leadership is strongly affected by the situation from which the leader emerges and in which they operate. Jumare (2015) argued that a particular leadership style might be best for a particular situation, but this inherently implies that leaders must match followers' needs in a certain situation. Blanchard (1996), as cited in McLaurin (2006, P 102), argued that the two behaviors (task and relationship) underpin four degrees of situational leadership styles:

- i. Telling style (S1) high task weak relationship behavior.
- ii. Selling style (S2) high task-high relationship behavior
- iii. Participating style (S3) low task-high relationship behavior
- iv. Delegating style (S4), low task-low relationship behavior.

Harsey and Blanchard (1946), as cited in North house (2007 P. 98), defined the four developmental levels as follows:

- i. Level 1 (unwilling and unable)
- ii. Level 2 (willing and unable)
- iii. Level 3 (unwilling and able) and
- iv. Level 4 (willing and able).

The four situational leadership styles depend on the follower developmental level combined with their ability and willingness. The telling style is a style a leader exhibits by giving guidance to followers who have low ability and willingness. Selling styles refer to a style a leader exhibits when followers require direct guidance and have low ability and high willingness. Finally, delegating style refers to the style a leader exhibits when followers have high ability and willingness to accept responsibility (Kao and Kao 2007). Situational leadership style is also

known as contingency theory (TI) in the 1960s and 1970s. Factors unique to each situation determine whether specific leader characteristics and behaviors are effective. Situational theories of Leadership style practices propose that the organizational or work group context affects the extent to which certain leader traits and behaviors are effective. Situational theories gained prominence in the late 1960s and 1970s. Four of the more well-known "Situational or Contingency Theories" are Fiedler's contingency theory, path-goal theory, the Vroom-Yetton-Jago decision-making model of leadership theory. Each of these leadership approaches is briefly described in the following sections.

Introduced in 1967, Fiedler's contingency/situational theory was the first to specify how situational factors interact with leader traits and behavior to influence leadership effectiveness. The theory suggests that the "favorability" of the situation determines the effectiveness of task- and person-oriented leader behaviors. The preference is determined by

- i. Respect and trust that followers have for the leader;
- ii. The extent to which subordinate responsibilities can be structured and performance measured; and
- iii. The control the leader has over subordinates' rewards. The situation is most favorable when followers respect and trust the leader, the task is highly structured, and the leader has control over rewards and punishments.

Fiedler's theory in (1967) indicated that task-oriented leaders were more effective when the situation was either highly favorable or highly unfavorable, but that person-oriented leaders were more effective in moderately favorable or unfavorable situations. The theory did not necessarily propose that leaders could adapt their leadership styles to different situations, but that leaders with different leadership styles would be more effective when placed in situations that matched their preferred style. Fiedler's situational/contingency theory has been criticized on both conceptual and methodological grounds. However, empirical research has supported many specific propositions of the theory and remains an important contributor to the understanding of leadership effectiveness.

Path-goal theory was first presented in a 1971 Administrative Science Quarterly article by Robert House. Path-goal theory proposes that subordinates' characteristics and work environment characteristics determine which leader behaviors are more effective. The key characteristics of subordinates identified by the theory are locus of control, work experience, ability, and the need for affiliation. The important environmental characteristics identified by the theory are the task, the formal authority system, and the work group. The theory includes four leader behaviors: directive leadership, supportive leadership, participative leadership, and achievement-oriented leadership.

According to Path-goal theory (1971), leader behavior should reduce barriers to subordinates' goal attainment, strengthen subordinates' expectancies that improved performance will lead to valued rewards, and provide coaching to make the path to payoffs easier for subordinates. Path-goal theory suggests that the leader's behavior that accomplishes these tasks depends on subordinate and environmental contingency factors. The path-goal theory has been criticized because it does not consider interactions among the contingency factors and because of the complexity of its underlying theoretical model, expectancy theory. Empirical research has provided support for the theory's propositions, primarily in relation to directive and supportive leader behaviors.

The Vroom-Yetton-Jago decision-making model was introduced by (Victor Vroom and Phillip Yetton in 1993). The theory focuses primarily on the degree to which subordinate participation is appropriate in different situations. Thus, it emphasizes the decision-making style of the leader. According to Jago (1998);

1. Contingency theory tends to focus more on behaviors that leaders should adopt given situational factors (often about follower behavior).
2. Contingency theory takes a broader view that includes contingent factors about leader capability and other variables within the situation. (Leaders who are very effective at one place and time may become unsuccessful in the other).

Authoritarianism
 Authority and control

- Unwillingness to delegate
- Top-down communication
- Information
- Tight control

Underestimation of subordinate competence

- Ignore subordinate suggestions
- Belittle subordinate contributions

Imagine building

- Act in a dignified manner
- Exhibiting high self-confidence

Didactic behavior

- Insist on high-performance standards
- Reprimand subordinates for poor performance

Compliance

- Public support
- Avoid open conflicts with the boss
- Avoid expressing dissension

Obedience

- Accept leader directives unconditionally
- Loyalty to the leader

Respect and fear

- Demonstrating deep respect
- Express fear in the awe of the leader

A sense of shame

- Willing to confess mistakes
- Take the leader's instructions seriously
- Correct mistakes and improve

Benevolent Leadership
 Individualized Care

- Treat employees as family members
- Provide job security
- Assist during personal crises
- Express holistic concern
- Avoid embarrassing subordinates in public
- Protect even grave errors of subordinates

Show gratitude

- Never forget the leader's favors

Strive to reciprocate

- Sacrifice self-interest for leadership

Compliance

- Public support
- Avoid open conflicts with the boss
- Avoid expressing dissension

Obedience

- Accept leader directives unconditionally
- Loyalty to the leader

Respect and fear

- Demonstrating deep respect
- Express fear in the awe of the leader

A sense of shame

- Willing to confess mistakes
- Take the leader's instructions seriously
- Correct mistakes and improve
- Take assignments seriously
- Meet leader's expectation
- Work diligently

Leaders' morality and integrity
 Unselfishness

- Does not abuse authority for personal gain
- Do not mix personal interests with business interests
- Put collective interests over personal interests

Example: Lead by example

- As an example in work and personal conduct

Identification

- Identifying with leaders' values and goals
- Internalize leaders' values

Modeling

- Imitate the behavior of leaders

Moreover, Pellegrini and Scandura (2008) claimed that paternalism is an effective leadership style in many non-Western cultures, mainly because paternalistic leaders are both benevolent and authoritarian. Paternalism is a word derived from the Latin root “pater,” meaning “father.” The leader assumes the role of a parent who knows best (Öner, 2012). Paternalism in leadership has existed throughout history and seems to derive its power from the psychological experiences of families in which the father plays a particular leadership role. Fu et al. (2013) asserted that paternalistic leadership is a managerial approach that involves a dominant authority figure who acts as a patriarch or matriarch and treats employees and partners as though they are members of a large extended family. In exchange, the leader expects loyalty, trust, and obedience from employees. Sunday (2014) opines that regardless of what word is used to describe parent employees who work in such an environment, they are expected to understand that the authority figure knows what is best for the organization and trust that their leader will always have an employee’s best interest at heart. Employees are listened to, but the leader always makes the final decision.

5. Methodology

The study used descriptive research and surveys were conducted through the use of a self-structured questionnaire to elicit response from; (a) School heads (b) teachers (c) Ministry of Education officials, and (d) Executive of Parent Teachers’ Association with a sample size of 1,425, comprising 345 school heads, 382 teachers, 321 MOE officials, and 378 PTA executives. The questionnaire was distributed to all respondents by the researchers and research assistant within the localized setting of secondary schools in the north-central part of Nigeria. Four sample of participants were used for this study (a) School heads (b) teachers, (c) Ministry of Education officials, and (d) PTA Executives from 7 states in the North-central part of Nigeria. The 345 school heads responded to the questionnaires, which represented 100% of all the 382 teachers also responded to the questionnaires, which represented 100% of the same with the Officials of Ministry of Education and Executive Officials of Parents Teachers’ Association, which represented 100% each respectively.

A sample is a portion drawn from the population to be studied. It is what the researcher selects for the purpose of data collection and analysis. For the purpose of this research, a Research Advisor (2006) at a 0.05 confidence level was used to determine the sample size of the state, School heads, teachers, the MOE and PTA ExcOs officials. The total sample size was one thousand four hundred and twenty-six (1,426). This consisted of 345 School heads, 382 teachers, 321 MOE officials, and 378 PTA Officials. The percentage of the population was used together with the total sample size obtained through the research advisor.

6. Results

Respondents’ Perceptions about the Stakeholders’ Perceptions of School Heads’ Situational Leadership style on Teachers’ Productivity.

In this section, the perceptions of respondents were sought on the stakeholders’ perceptions of School heads’ situational Leadership style practices in secondary schools in the North Central Geographical Zone of Nigeria. Table 2 shows the perceptions of the respondents regarding the stakeholders’ perceptions of School heads’ situational Leadership style practices in secondary schools in the North Central Geographical Zone of Nigeria. In the table, the perceptions are presented as frequencies and percentages.

Table 2: Perceptions of Respondents about the Stakeholders' Perceptions of School heads' Situational Leadership Style on Teachers' Productivity

S/N	Items statement	Category of Respondents	Agree		Undecided		Disagree	
			F.	%	F.	%	F.	%
1	School Heads allow teachers and students to participate actively in school activities that enhance productivity.	School Heads	338	98.0	7	2.0	0	0
		Teachers	360	94.2	20	5.2	2	0.5
		MOE	303	94.4	16	5.0	2	0.6
		PTA	357	94.4	19	5.0	2	0.5
2	School heads supervise teaching and learning actively through constant classroom visitations, which contribute to high productivity among teachers.	School Heads	337	97.7	8	2.3	0	0
		Teachers	369	96.6	11	2.9	2	0.5
		MOE	312	97.2	7	2.2	2	0.6
		PTA	366	96.8	10	2.6	2	0.5
3	My school head gives specific instructions on how some assignments should be completed.	School Heads	331	95.9	13	3.8	1	0.3
		Teachers	350	91.6	21	5.5	11	2.9
		MOE	309	96.3	9	2.8	3	0.9
		PTA	347	91.8	20	5.3	11	2.9
4	School heads use different styles as needs arise in the school, which keeps the staff and students up and doing in order to boost teachers' productivity.	School Heads	320	92.8	21	6.1	4	1.2
		Teachers	352	92.1	22	5.8	8	2.1
		MOE	299	93.1	16	5.0	6	1.9
		PTA	349	92.3	22	5.8	7	1.9
5	School heads display great integrity in their handling of challenging issues as the situation arises.	School Heads	339	98.3	6	1.7	0	0
		Teachers	357	93.5	17	4.5	8	2.1
		MOE	314	97.8	5	1.6	2	0.6
		PTA	354	93.7	17	4.5	7	1.9

In response to items 1 to 5, which sought the stakeholders' perceptions of school heads' situational leadership style on teachers' productivity in the North Central Geographical Zone of Nigeria., responses of all respondents were collected, analyzed and discussed.

Response to item 1 reveals that 338 (98.0%) school heads agreed that school heads allow teachers and students to participate actively in school activities that enhance productivity. However, 7 (2.0%) school heads were undecided. While 360 (94.2%) teachers agreed, 2 (0.5%) disagreed, and 20 (5.2%) were undecided. Among the ministry of education officials, 303 (94.4%) agreed, 2 (0.5%) disagreed, and 16 (5.0%) were undecided. In addition, 357 (94.4%) of the PTA agreed, while 2 (0.5%) disagreed and 19 (5.0%) were undecided. In all, the respondents showed a greater magnitude of their response that School heads allow teachers and students to participate actively in school activities to enhance teachers' productivity in the North Central Geographical Zone of Nigeria. The result shows that they are affirmative. In response to item 2, 337 (97.7%) school heads agreed that school heads supervise teaching and learning actively through constant classroom visitation, which contributes to high productivity, whereas 8 (2.3%) were undecided. While 369 (96.6%) teachers agreed, 2 (0.5%) disagreed, and an insignificant number of respondents 11 (2.9%) were undecided. Among the ministry of education officials, 312 (97.2%) agreed, 2 (0.6%) disagreed, and 11 (2.9%) were undecided. In addition, 366 (96.8%) of the PTA agreed, 2 (0.5%) disagreed, and 10 (2.6%) were undecided. In all, the respondents showed a greater magnitude of their response that School heads supervise teaching and learning actively through constant classroom visitation, which enhances high productivity among teachers in the school in the North Central

Geographical Zone of Nigeria. The result shows that they are affirmative. Based on the respondents' perceptions on items 3, 4, and 5, where no respondent had less than 75% in respect of disagreement, it is evident that there were positive perceptions from the respondents toward School heads' situational Leadership style practices on teachers' productivity in secondary schools in the North Central Geographical Zone, Nigeria. It was agreed that school heads give specific instructions on how some assignment should be done. School heads use different styles as the need arises in the school which keeps the staff and students up and doing. School heads display great integrity in their handling of challenging issues as the situation arises in the school in the North Central Geographical Zone, Nigeria.

Respondents' Perceptions of Stakeholders on School heads' Paternalistic Leadership style practices on teachers' productivity in Secondary Schools in North Central Geographical Zone, Nigeria.

In this section, the perceptions of respondents were sought on the perceptions of stakeholders' perceptions of school heads' paternalistic Leadership style practices on teachers' productivity in secondary schools in the North Central Geographical Zone of Nigeria. Table 3 shows the perceptions of the respondents regarding the perceptions of stakeholders' perceptions of school heads' paternalistic Leadership style practices on teachers' productivity in secondary schools in the North Central Geographical Zone of Nigeria. In the table, the perceptions are presented as frequencies and percentages.

Table 2: Respondents' Perceptions of Stakeholders' Perceptions of School heads' Paternalistic Leadership style practices in Secondary Schools in North Central Geographical Zone, Nigeria

S/N	Items statement	Category of Respondents	of Agree		Undecided		Disagree	
			F.	%	F.	%	F.	%
6	Teachers' views and decisions are respected by school heads, which results in high productivity.	School heads	332	96.2	6	1.7	7	2.0
		Teachers	364	95.3	8	2.1	10	2.6
		MOE	310	96.9	5	1.6	6	1.9
		PTA	362	95.8	8	2.1	8	2.1
7	Subordinate staff are treated by school heads as extended family, which leads to effectiveness and efficiency.	School heads	336	97.4	3	0.9	6	1.7
		Teachers	369	96.6	3	0.8	10	2.6
		MOE	313	97.5	3	0.9	5	1.6
		PTA	360	95.2	8	2.1	10	2.6
8	My school heads treat staff and students' welfare as a family this encourage productivity among teachers.	School heads	336	97.4	3	0.9	6	1.7
		Teachers	369	96.6	7	1.8	6	1.6
		MOE	314	97.8	5	1.6	2	0.6
		PTA	365	96.6	7	1.9	6	1.6
9	The staff and students are given fair treatment by my school heads, which encourages high productivity among teachers.	School heads	337	97.7	2	0.6	6	1.7
		Teachers	370	96.9	2	0.5	10	2.6
		MOE	313	97.5	2	0.6	6	1.9
		PTA	366	96.8	2	0.5	10	2.6
10	There is fairness in delegating duties to teachers by school heads, which fosters harmonious working relationships.	School heads	323	93.5	9	2.6	13	3.8
		Teachers	355	92.9	10	2.6	17	4.5
		MOE	301	93.8	8	2.5	12	3.7
		PTA	351	92.9	10	2.6	17	4.5

In response to items 6 to 10, which sought the stakeholders' perceptions of School heads' paternalistic Leadership style practices on teachers' productivity in secondary schools in the North Central Geographical Zone of Nigeria., responses of all respondents were collected, analyzed and discussed. Response to item 6 reveals that 332 (96.2%)

school heads agreed that teachers' views and decisions are respected, which results in high productivity among teachers. However, 7 (2.0%) disagreed and 6 (1.7%) were undecided with the statement. Among teachers, 364 (95.3%) of teachers agreed, 10 (2.6) disagreed, and 8 (2.1%) were undecided. 310 (96.9%) of MOE agreed, 5 (1.6) were undecided, and 6 (1.9%) disagreed with the statement. 362 (95.8%) of PTA agreed, 8 (2.1%) were undecided, and 8 (2.1%) disagreed that teachers' views and decisions are respected by the school heads in the North Central Geographical Zone of Nigeria. In response to item 7, 336 (97.4%) school heads agreed that subordinate staff are treated by the school heads as extended family in the school to encourage high productivity among teachers, 6 (1.7%) disagreed, and 3 (0.9%) of the school heads were undecided. While 369 (96.6%) teachers agreed, 10 (2.6%) disagreed, and insignificant number of respondents 3 (0.8%) were undecided. Among the ministry of education officials, 313 (97.5%) agreed, 5 (1.6%) disagreed, and 3 (0.9%) were undecided. In addition, 360 (95.2%) of the PTA agreed, whereas 10 (2.6%0) disagreed and 8 (2.1%) were undecided. In all, the respondents showed a greater magnitude of their response that subordinate staff are treated by school heads as extended family in the school in the North Central Geographical Zone of Nigeria. The result shows that they are affirmative. Based on the respondents' perceptions on items 8, 9, and 10, where no respondent had less than 75% in respect of disagreement, it is evident that there were negative perceptions from the respondents toward School heads' paternalistic Leadership style practices on teachers' productivity in secondary schools in the North Central Geographical Zone, Nigeria. It was agreed that school heads treat staff and students' welfare as a family in the school. Staff and students are given fair treatment by the school heads, and there is fairness in delegating duties to teachers by the school heads, which results in high productivity among teachers in the North Central Geographical Zone, Nigeria.

Hypotheses Testing

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant difference among the perceptions of school heads, teachers, officials of the Ministry of Education, and PTA officials on School heads' situational Leadership style practices on teachers' productivity in secondary schools in the North Central Geographical Zone, Nigeria.

The responses of the respondents on items 1 to 10 were collected and analyzed to find out the school heads' situational Leadership style practices on teachers' productivity in secondary schools in North Central Geographical Zone, Nigeria. A One-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) statistical procedure was employed as shown in table 4.

Table 4 shows the mean score of the perceptions of School heads, teachers, officials of the Ministry of Education, and PTA officials on School heads' situational Leadership style practices on teachers' productivity in secondary schools in the North Central Geographical Zone, Nigeria. A significant difference.

Table 3: Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) on stakeholders' perceptions of school heads' Situational Leadership style practices on teachers' productivity in Secondary Schools in North Central Geographical Zone, Nigeria

Source	Sum of squares	DF	Mean Square	F-ratio	F-critical	P-value
Among groups	23.527	3	7.842	08.509	16.605	1.09
Within groups	671.589	1422	.472			
Total	695.116	1425				

In table 4, the computed probability was 1.09, which was higher than the p-value of 0.05 for this study. In other words, the calculated F- ratio value of 08.509 was less than the critical value of 16.605, while the calculated P-value of 1.09 was greater than the 0.05 level of significance. Therefore, the null hypothesis (Ho6) was retained.

It can be concluded that there were no significant differences among the perceptions of School heads, teachers, officials of the Ministry of Education, and PTA officials on School heads' situational Leadership style practices on teachers' productivity in secondary schools in the North Central Geographical Zone, Nigeria.

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant difference among the perceptions of school heads, teachers, officials of the Ministry of Education, and PTA officials on School heads' paternalistic Leadership style practices on teachers' productivity in secondary schools in the North Central Geographical Zone, Nigeria.

The responses of the respondents on items 1 to 10 were collected and analyzed to determine the school heads' paternalistic Leadership style practices on teachers' productivity in secondary schools in North Central Geographical Zone, Nigeria. A One-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) statistical procedure was employed as shown in table 5. Table 5 shows the mean score of the perceptions of School heads, teachers, officials of the Ministry of Education, and PTA officials on School heads' paternalistic Leadership style practices on teachers' productivity in secondary schools in the North Central Geographical Zone, Nigeria. A significant difference.

Table 5: Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) on stakeholders' perceptions of school heads' Paternalistic Leadership style practices on teachers' productivity in Secondary Schools in North Central Geographical Zone, Nigeria

Source	Sum of squares	DF	Mean Square	F-ratio	F-critical	P-value
Among groups	55.630	3	18.543	20.701	17.494	.03
Within groups	702.299	1422	.495			
Total	757.930	1425				

Result of table 5 shows that significant differences existed among School heads, teachers, officials of the Ministry of Education, and PTA officials on School heads' paternalistic Leadership style practices on teachers' productivity in secondary schools in the North Central Geographical Zone, Nigeria. The computed probability was .03, which was less than the p-value of 0.05 in this study. In other words, the calculated F-ratio value of 20.701 was greater than the critical value of 17.494, while the calculated P-value of .03 was less than the 0.05 level of significance. Therefore, the null hypothesis (H_0) was rejected. It can be concluded that there were significant differences among the perceptions of School heads, teachers, officials of the Ministry of Education, and PTA officials on School heads' paternalistic Leadership style practices on teachers' productivity in secondary schools in the North Central Geographical Zone, Nigeria.

7. Conclusions

In response to items 1 to 5, which sought the stakeholders' perceptions of School heads' situational Leadership style practices on teachers' productivity in the North Central Geographical Zone of Nigeria., responses of all respondents were collected, analyzed and discussed. Based on the respondents' perceptions where no respondent had less than 75% in respect of disagreement, it is evident that there were positive perceptions from the respondents toward School heads' situational Leadership style practices in secondary schools in the North Central Geographical Zone, Nigeria. It was agreed that school heads give specific instructions on how some assignment should be done. They use different styles as the need arises in the school which keeps the staff and students up and doing. They display great integrity in their handling of challenging issues as the situation arises in the school which had positive effect on teachers' productivity in the North Central Geographical Zone, Nigeria as the computed probability of 1.09 was obtained, which was higher than the 0.05 level of significance set for the study. This was supported by Olu (2014), who opined that, in situational leadership styles, leaders choose the best course

of action based on situational conditions or circumstances. In addition, a leader's influence can only be effective by being in the right place at the right time (Bagobiri & Kassah, 2009). However, the researcher opined that several studies have been conducted on the grounds that leadership is strongly affected by the situation from which the leader emerges and in which he or she operates. The results of the study revealed that no significant difference existed between a particular frame of situational leadership style and student achievement among elementary school heads in Mississippi. The study also revealed that no significant difference existed between a combination of frames of situational leadership styles and student achievement among elementary school heads in Mississippi.

8. Conclusion

The study concludes that situational leadership style does not have any relationship with student achievement. The findings show that public school teachers in North Carolina are at a moderate level of readiness to perform with school heads using situational leadership styles that involve delegation style of leadership as the P-value was .789, which was greater than the 0.05 level of significance set for the study. The findings also revealed that a relationship exists between years of teaching experience and teacher readiness to perform teaching tasks under school heads with a situational leadership style, as the p.value was .659. In support of this, Evans (2012) opined that school heads who use a paternalistic leadership style will always recognize that he is working with teachers, students and others who are capable of being part of decision making. He further stressed that it is important for the administration to realize and act upon the realization that many teachers are well qualified and experienced and can become school heads. Hence, to achieve the objectives,

9. Recommendations

The following recommendations were raised:

1. Staff are to be involved in decision making, which does not alter the fact that school heads remain accountable for making final decisions.
2. The researchers also conceptualized paternalistic leadership style practices as the act of determining a course of action following a nearly deliberate consideration of completing alternatives.

References

- Adetoro, M. A. (2009). *Introduction to Research Methodology*. Published and Printed by CAPS Publishing Company.
- Adeyemi, S. O. (2010). School Heads' Leadership Style and Teachers' Job Performance in Senior Secondary Schools in Ondo State. *Journal of Education*, Vol. 10, 110-119.
- Ahmad, J. U. (2011). Leadership and Challenges and Way Forward. *Journal of Educational Administration* 40(2) 40-55
- Bagobiri, E.Y. & Kassah, V. (2009). *Principles of Management*, published by The Great Press.
- Bass, B. M. (2014). From Transactional to Transformational Leadership. Learning to share the vision organizational dynamics <http://doc.org.com>
- Brenda, K. H. (2011). Teachers' Perceptions of their school heads' leadership style and effect on students' achievement in improving and non-improving schools. Ph.D. thesis, Florida University.

- David, V. U. (2012). Effect of School Head Leadership Style on the School Environment in some Secondary Schools in Nassarawa State. Unpublished Ph.D. thesis.
- Deepak, B., Rajiv, R., Suman, S & Vishal, J. (2013). Perception of various Stakeholders about principal as a school leader. An exploratory study. <https://www.researchgate.net/publication317973632>
- Fan, J.I. and Change, B.S. (2006). Paternalistic Leadership Scale Construct and Measurement of the three-element model. *Indigenous Psychology Research*. Vol. 14, Pg. 31-40.
- Fu, X.I., Li Y, Si X (2013). The Impact of Paternalistic Leadership on Innovation. An Integrated Model, *Nankai Business Review International* Vol. 4(ii), pp. 9-24. [Http://www.businessreview.com](http://www.businessreview.com)
- Hafiz, M. and Khansa, H. (2017). The Impact of Paternalistic Leadership Style on Employee Job Satisfaction, Investigating the Dimensions of Paternalistic Leadership Proceedings of 9th Annual American Business Research Conference, New York, USA.
- Haruna, J.E. & Omuya, F. O. (2022). Impact of Collaborative Leadership on Quality Assurance for Goal Attainment of Universities in Kogi State. *KIU Interdisciplinary Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences*, 3(2) 289-304.
- Hassan, H. (2011). Leadership Styles, Decision-making Styles, and Teachers' Job Satisfaction. An Indonesian School Context. Unpublished Ph.D. thesis, James Cook University.
- Jago, M. A. (1998). Leadership Effect on Small-Scale Medium Enterprise (www.leadership.com)
- Jumane, A. M. (2015). Introduction to Educational Management Ethics through Concept Designs and Prints.
- Kao, P.H. & Kao, H.I. (2007). Taiwanese Executive Leadership Styles and the Decision-Making Models They Use in Mainland China. *Journal of America Academy of Business*. Cambridge. Vol. 10 (page71-79).
- Marzano, R. J. (2015). School Leadership and Curriculum Association for Supervision and Curriculum Development. www.curriculumcontent.com
- McLaurin, J. R. (2006). The role of the situation in the Leadership Process. A Review and Application *Academic Strategic Management Journal*. Vol. 5(i) 102-112.
- Northhouse, P. G. (2007). *A Leadership Theory Practice*. 2nd Edition. Thousand Oaks.
- Obonyo, P.M., Adino, G.O. & Nyerere, J. (2017). Leadership Styles practiced by School heads in Public Secondary Schools in Siaya Kasumu and Kajiado Countries Kenya-*European Journal of Education Studies*. Vol. 3(9).
- Olu, E. I. (2014). School head leadership in the process of literacy reform. A Structure Conceptualization, *International Journal of Education*. Vol. 1(2). Pg. 20-30.

- Omuya, A. F. Adegbite, I. P. & Duze, D. A. (2021). Stakeholders' Perceptions of School heads, Leadership Styles Practices in Secondary Schools in North Central Geographical Zone, Nigeria. *KIU Interdisciplinary Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences* Vol. 2(2) 48-64.
- Pellegrim, E.K. & Scandura, T. A. (2008). Paternalistic Leadership. A Review and Agenda for Future Research. *Journal of Management*. Vol. Thirty-four pg. 566-593.
- Peter, G.A (2015) Relationship between Leadership Styles Used by Headteachers of Public Secondary Schools and Students' Academic Performance. *Journal of Education* Vol. 5(2) pg. 9-20 Mount Kenyan University.